

Geometric Transformation-Based Data Augmentation on Defect Classification of Segmented Images of Semiconductor Materials Using a ResNet50 Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract

The emergence of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques opens a huge opportunity for their implementation in industry. One of the tasks for which these techniques have the greatest potential is visual inspection, since both ML and DL techniques are able to determine relationships between large volumes of data. However, these techniques require large volumes of images that cannot always be captured. As a solution to this, data augmentation techniques are applied. In this work, starting from a highly imbalanced dataset containing images of different semiconductor defects, several datasets are generated using data augmentation techniques based on geometric transformations. A [ResNet50 convolutional neural network](#) is then fed with each of the datasets to analyze the effect of data augmentation on its classification performance. The results reveal that, with an adequate number

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of synthetic images of the minority classes, the F1-score improves by 3.74% over that obtained with the original dataset.

Keywords:

Data augmentation, Convolutional neural networks, Semiconductor device manufacturing, Inspection systems

1. Introduction

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) in the last years has been impressive. This development involves the implementation of AI in multiple applications that most people use in their daily lives (Koch, 2018; Lee, 2020; Górriz et al., 2020). However, the application of AI in industry is challenging in many cases (Bécue et al., 2021; Mao et al., 2019; Ahmad et al., 2021). One of the branches of AI whose application has an enormous potential, especially when applied to inspection systems in industry, is computer vision (Brosnan and Sun, 2004; Saeidi et al., 2005; Leta et al., 2008; Roda-Sanchez et al., 2021). Within computer vision techniques, there are two which deserve especial attention due to their ability to deal with large volumes of data and find the relationship between them: machine learning (ML) and, mainly, deep learning (DL) (Gheisari et al., 2017).

Although ML and DL methods may appear to be very new, many of them were developed decades ago. However, it is only now that the power of computers and graphics processing units (GPU) has increased when all these methods and models can be applied to different tasks (Han et al., 2018). As mentioned before, one of these potential tasks is computer vision applied to inspection systems. A basic architecture for an inspection system incorporating ML or DL techniques would consist of the inspection device(s) or sensors (cameras, optical microscopes, scanning electron microscopes (SEM), etc.), a workstation computer and actuators or displays (Villalba-Diez et al., 2019; Ismail and Malik, 2021; Gómez-Sirvent et al., 2022). First, the sensors or inspection systems acquire the data (i.e. images) and send them to the workstation computer. As the data usually requires preprocessing, an automated preprocessing module prepares the images prior to input into the ML or DL model. ML and DL models are usually integrated together with the preprocessing module (Hijazi et al., 2015). The common trend is to use Python as the programming language because of its low complexity and the large number of available open libraries and commercial models. Finally, the

model's output is simply displayed or a signal is delivered to actuators to automatically classify the samples.

However, it is still common to employ a human operator to review and classify the defective products along an assembly line. Depending on the industry and its characteristics, these operators may be equipped with different visual inspection devices, ranging from a magnifying glass to a scanning electron microscope. It is well known that human operators suffer from occupational stress, visual fatigue and other diseases related to their tedious and hard work (Yeow and Nath Sen, 2004). These illnesses lead to a drop in their performance and, consequently, failures, which as well incur in costs. Therefore, investing in developing ML and DL models that could assist or even replace those operators is a great opportunity to increment industry's revenues while improving the working conditions of these operators (López de la Rosa et al., 2021).

Industrial environments are immersed in continuous change and chaos. There is too much noise and pollutants that can alter manufactured products, leading to different kinds of defects. The proportion in which each defect appears is unique and different from the rest and may also vary over time. Consequently, when constructing the datasets used to train the ML and DL models to classify defects, there is a challenge that needs to be addressed: the imbalance between the number of images contained in each of the classes. This challenge is even greater in some DL methods, such as convolutional neural networks (CNN), which require thousands of images to obtain adequate results. There are three different approaches to deal with the imbalance: under sampling (when the number of images belonging to the minority classes is sufficient to train the model and the only operation to perform is to randomly remove images from the majority classes), oversampling (when the number of images belonging to the minority or even majority classes is not sufficient and it is necessary to generate synthetic images) or a hybrid approach.

In this work, the focus will be on the oversampling strategy. Synthetic images will be generated using data augmentation techniques based on image transformations. With the aim to analyze the influence of this data augmentation on the performance of the classifier [in an incremental way](#), we will prepare different datasets (each with more synthetic images than the previous one) with which a [ResNet50](#) CNN will be trained. The images come from the semiconductor manufacturing industry. Specifically, there are up to seven different classes of defects found in semiconductor wafers. The images have

been captured using a SEM device. Therefore, we will evaluate the performance of the classifier with different performance metrics when trained with each of the prepared datasets to find the relationship between the number of synthetic images generated and the performance of the classifier.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 consists of a review of the different approaches and techniques that can be applied to perform data augmentation, finally focusing on those based on image transformations. Section 3 is devoted to explaining the different steps (data collection, data preprocessing, model presentation, model training, and metrics) that have been followed to develop the experiments. Section 4 collects every result obtained in the experiments and their discussion. Finally, the section 5 sets out the conclusions of this work and presents future lines of research.

2. Data Augmentation

When there are not enough images to train a model properly, or the classes present a huge imbalance between them, oversampling is the most appropriate approach to obtain acceptable classification results. Usually, this oversampling is carried out by means of data augmentation techniques. Data augmentations makes the classifiers able to generalize and gain robustness in classification (Zhang et al., 2022). Data augmentation techniques can be grouped in two large groups: deep learning approaches and image manipulation (Shorten and Khoshgoftaar, 2019). All the techniques that will be briefly described along this paper are shown in Figure 1.

2.1. Deep Learning Approaches

Along with the emergence of dedicated DL methods for image classification, some novel data augmentation methods using DL have burst onto the scene. Within these methods, two of them deserve especial attention: generative adversarial networks (GAN) (Goodfellow et al., 2014) and neural style transfer (NST) (Gatys et al., 2015).

Generative adversarial networks. GAN have proven to be capable of producing realistic synthetic data, most notably their application to generate synthetic images (Shao et al., 2019). GAN couple a generator and a discriminator. The generator generates new images from the original data. Then, the discriminator validates the generated images comparing them with the

Figure 1: Data augmentation techniques.

original ones and rejects the ones that are not suitable. So, first, the network extracts the features from the initial data, and, in a second stage, it merges those features to generate new data. In other words, the discriminator is trained to distinguish synthetic samples from real ones, and, the generator, is trained to deceive the discriminator (Shi et al., 2018). Figure 2 illustrates schematically how GAN work. There are uncountable works which have used GAN to perform image data augmentation (Frid-Adar et al., 2018; Sarker et al., 2021; Iglesias Morís et al., 2021; Elakkiya et al., 2021). However, the challenge of performing data augmentation using GAN will be addressed in future works.

Neural style transfer. NST consists of transferring the style of one image to another without altering its content by using CNNs. In other words, NST is the process of using CNNs to represent an image in different styles (Jing et al., 2019). Figure 3 shows an example of an image to which NST has been applied. At first glance, one might think that NST is a method dedicated solely to artistic applications. However, due to the fact that it represents the same content in many different styles, it can be used to generate several images from an original one. Therefore, it may be used for data augmentation issues as it has been proved in different contributions (Cicalese et al., 2020; Jackson et al., 2019). Despite its use in those works, NST does not seem to

Figure 2: GAN diagram.

Figure 3: NST example (Elgendy, 2020).

be the most appropriate data augmentation method for our particular case.

2.2. Image Manipulation Approaches

Data augmentation based on image manipulation approaches is much less complex and more traditional than that based on deep learning approaches. These techniques consist in generating new images by performing simple transformations on the original images. Some techniques that should be considered and, therefore, will be explained are the use of kernels, random erasing, mixing images, color-space transformation and geometric transformation.

Use of kernels. The use of kernels or filters is widespread in image preprocessing, mainly to remove noise. Although there are different kernels that can be used to manipulate the image, probably the most commonly used are the Gaussian filter, the mean filter and the median filter. To generate a new

Figure 4: Median, Gaussian and mean filters.

image, these filters are used to blur and sharpen the images. The truth is that this data augmentation technique is relatively unexplored. In general, it is not often used because of its similarity to the internal mechanisms that CNNs have (Shorten and Khoshgoftaar, 2019). For this reason, this technique has not been used for augmenting our dataset. Figure 4 illustrates the transformation an image suffers when the filters mentioned above are applied to it.

Random erasing. As its name reveals, random erasing technique consists in randomly erasing parts of the original image (Zhong et al., 2020). This simple mechanism is really useful to avoid overfitting, as it forces the model to focus on the whole image rather than on a single feature. With the aim of not losing relevant information if the defects are partly removed, this technique has not been implemented in this work.

Mixing images. Mixing images technique consists in merging different images to generate a new one. Although this sounds weird to human eye, this technique has been proved to offer good results with some well-known datasets (Dabouei et al., 2021; Harris et al., 2020; Inoue, 2018). However, it is true that mixing images is only useful in a limited range of applications. For this reason, we have decided to use other techniques to perform the data augmentation.

Color-space transformations. This technique includes a wide variety of operations that can be applied to an image. The most common ones include playing with the contrast and saturation of the image, adding a different color to the image pixels, etc. Different works have included this data augmentation technique to generate datasets (Kim et al., 2020; Xiao et al., 2019).

Although, in this work the authors have decided to perform the data augmentation based on geometric transformations, some color-space transformations could be included in the future to improve the quality of the dataset.

Geometric transformations. These techniques are, probably, the easiest ones to implement and offer great results when applied correctly. Those are the reasons because of which this approach has been adopted to perform the data augmentation in this work. Some of the techniques in this group are listed below (see Figure 5).

1. Scaling: this operation consists in changing the dimensions of the images. There are two ways of doing this, cropping the image to reduce its size or enlarging the image to make it larger.
2. Rotation: as the name suggests, in rotation technique the image is rotated by a certain angle between 0° and 360° . The center of rotation can be defined manually. However, it usually coincides with the center of the image.
3. Translation: this operation consists just in shifting the image through its X and Y axes.
4. Flipping: as its name reveals, this technique consists in flipping horizontally or vertically the pixels of the image.

Having explained the state of the art of data augmentation techniques and the particular focus of this work, it is time to present the methodology that has been followed in this work in Section 3.

3. Methodology

The methodology followed to carry out the experiments that have been developed in this work is collected in this section. Figure 6 shows each step that makes up the methodology.

3.1. Data Collection

The original images used in the experiments have been obtained by an SEM device along the first steps of the wafer fabrication chain. The original data were manually labeled by an expert and organized into eight different classes. However, the defect-free images will not be used to train the CNN model. Therefore, the model will be trained with only seven classes (see Figure 7).

Figure 5: Data augmentation based on geometric transformations.

Figure 6: Methodology.

Figure 7: Defects samples of each class.

The “No defect” class contains images without any kind of defect. Class 100 groups defects that have a non-homogeneous line shape. Class 150, which is similar to class 100, contains defects that are also line-shaped, but the defects tend to form a fairly homogeneous line in this case. Class 200 defects are irregular mounds or particles. Class 300 defects are in the form of hexagonal and pentagonal cavities. Class 350 defects are hexagonal and pentagonal in shape as in class 300, but there is always more than one cavity in the image. These multiple cavities may even overlap each other. Class 500 is a sort of combination of classes 300 and 200. These defects consist of an irregular cavity with a mound inside. Finally, Class 550 groups defects with a rounded shape. In addition, the size of each defect varies, although the difference in size is not noticeable in the images as these are automatically scaled. In this regards, the images include a scale bar to indicate the actual shape of the defect. The fact that the defects have approximately the same size in the images makes it easy to follow a same segmentation approach for each class.

Finally, the proportion in which each class appears in the original dataset is shown in Table 1 that shows the huge imbalance that exists between the different classes that compose the dataset. Obviously, as there is a small number of images of some of the classes, these will be really difficult to classify by the trained model. This is the reason why data augmentation should be applied.

Table 1: Distribution of images (original dataset)

Defect class	Count
No defect	227
Class 100	55
Class 150	8
Class 200	4,008
Class 300	1,068
Class 350	43
Class 500	289
Class 550	4

3.2. Data Preprocessing

To make the images suitable for model training, some preprocessing steps have to be followed. The first step is to homogenize the size of the images. Then, the images are cropped to remove the scale bar at the bottom of the images. Next, a defect segmentation process in which the defects are removed from the background is carried out. Finally, geometric transformations are applied to the segmented defects and a background is added to recreate the original images. These steps are listed and explained in more detail below.

3.2.1. Image resizing

There were two different image sizes in the dataset, 480×480 and 720×720 pixels. With the aim of homogenizing the image size, every image has been resized to a 480×480 pixels size.

3.2.2. Image cropping

As mentioned above, the scale bar at the bottom of the images has been removed by cropping the images. The new image size after this operation is 400×400 pixels. [Image cropping and resizing of the previous image do not involve relevant information loss.](#) The fact is that the defects are located in the center of the different images that make up the original dataset. It is true that two classes of defects tend to have an elongated shape (classes 100 and 150), but the loss of information is negligible, as the characteristics of the defects remain intact, being perfectly recognizable.

Figure 8: Segmented defect samples of each class.

3.2.3. Defect segmentation

In this step, the defect is removed from the background of the image so that future geometric transformations are applied to the defect rather than to the whole image. The defect segmentation is performed by combining a thresholding operation and a conditioned addition operation. Once applied the threshold, the background of the image will be white, while the defect will be black. The conditioned addition can be defined by means of this rule: if the pixel is white (255 intensity value), it will be replaced by black color (0 intensity value). Else, it will be replaced by the pixel value of the original image. [Figure 8](#) shows some images after defect segmentation.

3.2.4. Data augmentation

In this step, the data augmentation based on geometric transformations are applied to the original dataset (see [Figure 5](#)). Starting from the dataset resulting from removing the images used for validation from the original dataset ([DS1](#)), different datasets will be generated. Each one will contain twice as many images as the previous one. Each dataset contains twice as many images as the previous one. To define a limit to this increase, the maximum number of images per class will be the minimum of these two conditions:

Figure 9: Distribution of the datasets after data augmentation

1. 64 times the number of original images.
2. Same number of images as class 200, which is the majority class.

Thus, each class will be gradually increased until that maximum is reached. For example, if class 300 reaches the maximum in the second dataset generated, it will maintain the same number of images in the following datasets. So, we will work with 7 different datasets which will contain 1 (DS1), 2 (DS2), 4 (DS4), 8 (DS8), 16 (DS16), 32 (DS32) and 64 (DS64) times the number of images of the starting one, always fulfilling both previously mentioned conditions. Figure 9 clearly illustrates this procedure.

As can be seen in Figure 9, the datasets are still far from being balanced. However, the minority classes now contain enough images to train the model and the influence of the data augmentation on the performance metrics will then be clearly visible. [The behavior of the performance metrics with each incremental step in the number of images \(from DS1 to DS64\) will be discussed in Section 4.](#)

3.2.5. Background addition

Once the transformations have been applied, a background is added to the resulting images to recreate the original ones.

3.3. CNN Implementation

As introduced in the previous sections, a CNN model was used to analyze the effects of data augmentation on the classification results. CNNs are really powerful tools compared to other classifiers and to traditional computer vision algorithms when used in defect detection and classification (Ming et al., 2020). As aforementioned, the CNN model that was chosen to develop the experiments of this work is ResNet50 (He et al., 2016).

The settings of the model were obtained by using the grid search algorithm (Liashchynskyi and Liashchynskyi, 2019). [Grid search will manage two hyperparameters in this work: optimizer and learning rate \(LR\).](#) The CNN model will be trained with two different optimizers, stochastic gradient descent (SGD) (Robbins and Monro, 1951) and adaptive moment estimation (ADAM) (Kingma and Ba, 2014). On the other hand, LR will take values in the range $[10^{-1}, 10^{-6}]$ following a logarithmic scale. The optimal settings are collected in Table 2.

Table 2: ResNet50 configuration

CNN Model	Optimizer	LR	Batch Size	Loss function
ResNet50	SGD	10^{-2}	9	CCE

From Table 2, it can be seen that the optimizer used to train the model was SGD, while the LR was set to 10^{-2} . The batch size was fixed at 9, which is the maximum capacity of the GPU, while the loss function chosen was categorical cross entropy (CCE). [Random weight initialization was selected to train the model.](#)

The learning strategy adopted for this work is explained next. First, 10% of the images that make up the original dataset have been selected for validation. The distribution of this validation set will be the same as that of the original dataset, ensuring that every class is represented. The validation set will be the same for each of the generated datasets. Then, training and test sets are selected randomly from the rest of the images, consisting of 80% and 20% of the images respectively. With those sets, the model is trained and validated. This operation will be repeated for each of the generated datasets.

3.4. Performance Metrics

The evaluation of the model’s performance for each dataset will be carried out with the help of different performance metrics. Listed below are the performance metrics used for the evaluation of the model’s performance in the different experiments carried out in this research.

3.4.1. Precision (P)

Precision measures the fraction of correctly classified positive predictions out of the total number of positive predictions. It is obtained as follows:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

where TP represents true positives and FP denotes false positives. TP and FP are determined for each of the classes as in a binary classification scenario. For example, if we have 2 classes, “A” and “B”, a TP would be classifying an image of class “A” correctly as an image of class “A”, while a FP would be classifying an image of class “B” wrongly as an image of class “A”.

3.4.2. Recall (R)

Recall is defined as the proportion of positive predictions that are classified correctly. It is computed as follows:

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

where FN represents false negatives. Continuing with the above example, an FN would be an image of class “A” badly classified as an image of class “B”.

3.4.3. F1-score ($F1$)

F1-score represents the harmonic mean between P and R (Hossin and Sulaiman, 2015). This metric is calculated as follows.

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot P \cdot R}{P + R} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

The reason for choosing F1-score as the main metric for assessing the performance of the model when fed with the generated datasets is its suitability for evaluating imbalanced datasets (Cruz et al., 2016) such as those studied

in this work. Therefore, this metric will help the authors to judge the effect of data augmentation on the classification results.

4. Results and Discussion

Once the methodology followed in this work has been presented, the experiments that have been carried out are described. Every experiment in this work has been conducted with a workstation computer with the following hardware specifications: CPU Intel i7-10700KF v8 @ 3.80 GHz, 32 GB RAM, and NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 SUPER 8GB. The model has been trained with Keras and TensorFlow libraries. Pycharm and Python 3.8 have been chosen as the integrated development environment (IDE) and the programming language respectively.

As it was introduced in previous sections, the experiment conducted in this work consists in feeding the ResNet50 CNN model with the different datasets that have been generated by means of applying data augmentation techniques [to study how the classification performance varies after each incremental step in the number of images generated for the different datasets \(from DS1 to DS64\)](#). The classification performance is evaluated with the F1-score metric, ideal for scenarios where we work with imbalanced datasets.

The model is trained for one hundred consecutive epochs for each of the datasets. However, early stopping conditions are set, so that if the validation loss does not improve over ten consecutive iterations, the model stops training. Each experiment is repeated twenty times to ensure the reproducibility of the experiment. The results of this experiment are collected in Table 3.

The F1-scores obtained for each dataset over the twenty iterations are shown in the table. In order to visualize the results more clearly, the average F1-score obtained for each dataset has been calculated and plotted in Figure 10.

From Figure 10 it can be seen that the trend of the F1-score is clearly upward as the number of images generated increases. It can be observed that, for the second and third datasets, the F1-score is lower than that of the original dataset (DS1), probably because there are not enough images in the minority classes and the synthetic images are not perfect. There is a turning point when training the model with DS8, where the F1-score shoots up. Then, for the remaining data sets, the F1-score improves slightly, approaching 100%. [The asymptotic behavior of the F1-score metric along each incremental step is clearly noticeable. A computational effort in generating](#)

Table 3: F1-score for each iteration and dataset

It.	DS1	DS2	DS4	DS8	DS16	DS32	DS64
0	0.9885	0.9857	0.9885	0.9120	0.9934	0.9955	0.9973
1	0.9885	0.9863	0.9885	0.9915	0.9936	0.9961	0.9934
2	0.4265	0.9885	0.7206	0.9917	0.9934	0.9885	0.9982
3	0.9863	0.9863	0.9866	0.9917	0.9903	0.9918	0.9937
4	0.9863	0.9845	0.9885	0.9831	0.9934	0.9936	0.9955
5	0.9674	0.8706	0.9885	0.9918	0.9961	0.9936	0.9936
6	0.9864	0.9845	0.9885	0.9885	0.9867	0.9906	0.9955
7	0.9863	0.9863	0.9885	0.9883	0.9934	0.9930	0.9955
8	0.9885	0.9863	0.9623	0.9936	0.9973	0.9912	0.9954
9	0.9864	0.9878	0.9848	0.9906	0.9917	0.9907	0.9954
10	0.9885	0.9845	0.9885	0.9900	0.9903	0.9898	0.9954
11	0.9863	0.9845	0.9868	0.9936	0.9936	0.9934	0.9955
12	0.9885	0.8104	0.9863	0.9915	0.9916	0.9954	0.9954
13	0.9867	0.9863	0.9885	0.9885	0.9915	0.9934	0.9937
14	0.9844	0.9885	0.9885	0.9888	0.9903	0.9937	0.9955
15	0.9863	0.9848	0.9885	0.9869	0.9903	0.9981	0.9954
16	0.9863	0.9885	0.9885	0.9903	0.9916	0.9936	0.9955
17	0.9864	0.2798	0.9885	0.9885	0.9885	0.9934	0.9963
18	0.9863	0.9723	0.9795	0.9885	0.9918	0.9885	0.9955
19	0.9885	0.9608	0.3285	0.9866	0.9934	0.9912	0.9954

more and more synthetic images may not be worthwhile after a certain point. There is an improvement of a 3.74% in the F1-score from the original dataset to the seventh. This percentage may seem ridiculous from a point of view outside the semiconductor manufacturing industry. However, it should be noted that the proportion in which defects appear in production is approximately the same as in the initial data set. Therefore, this improvement may be the difference between classifying or misclassifying defects from one or more minority classes, which will make the difference between a good or a bad classifier.

5. Conclusions

In this work, the influence of data augmentation on the defect classification performance of a CNN model has been studied. According to the

Figure 10: Mean F1-score values for each dataset.

knowledge of previous research carried out by the authors of this work, the model chosen to perform this analysis has been ResNet50. Once reviewed the different techniques that make up the state-of-the-art of data augmentation, attention has been focused on the data augmentation techniques based on geometric transformations. These geometric transformations have been explained in detail and illustrated using different samples that have been used in this work.

Then, up to seven different datasets, each with twice as many images as the previous one within the limits defined by the conditions explained in previous sections, have been generated by applying this data augmentation techniques based on geometric transformations. Next, ResNet50 was fed with every generated dataset and the F1-score metric, ideal when dealing with imbalanced datasets, was used to evaluate the classification performance obtained by the model in each case.

The results revealed that the data augmentation procedure worked well, improving the classification results by a 3.74% which, for datasets with such an imbalance, may mean the difference between a great or a poor classifier. Therefore, the effect of data augmentation on the classification performance of the ResNet50 model has been analyzed, concluding that, with the generation of an adequate number of synthetic images for the minority classes, the performance of the model shoots up.

Finally, it should be noted that any work related to image classification faces some challenges. One of them is the response to disturbances. A typical solution is to put a preprocessing module prior to the CNN to remove or at least smooth the noise from the input images, thus facilitating the image classification task. In this work, as the images in the original dataset do not contain relevant noise, the effect of perturbations was not studied. Nevertheless, it is known that data augmentation improves the training of the CNN, making the model generalizable and able to correctly classify lower quality images.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations have been used in this manuscript:

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCE	Categorical cross-entropy
CNN	Convolutional neural network
DL	Deep learning
DS	Dataset
F1	F1-score
GAN	Generative adversarial network
GPU	Graphics processing unit
IDE	Integrated development environment
LR	Learning rate
ML	Machine learning
NST	Neural style transfer
P	Precision
R	Recall
SEM	Scanning electron microscope
SGD	Stochastic gradient descent

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